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Results of 5 kW SOFC CHP system development in the SOFC5-60 project

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Abstract

Continuous improvement of AVL's natural gas operated SOFC CHP platform towards residential and small industrial applications led to first operational tests of a completely new hardware generation, targeting 5 kW_{EL}, 55 % AC net electrical efficiency and 5000 h of operation. Within the scope of the publicly funded project "SOFC5-60" (FFG: 864851 / PtJ: 03ET6120A), conducted in cooperation with Fraunhofer IKTS, High Tech Coatings, BIOS Bioenergiesysteme GmbH, Viessmann, AVL Schrick and Forschung Burgenland from 2017 to 2021, the aim is to fully integrate and operate the system in an office building for the provision of electricity and hot water. Further target applications are hotels and apartment buildings. Therefore, electricity and heat demand profiles of such applications were analyzed to identify the optimal building sizes for a 5 kW system as well as the requirements for the operating procedure. AVLs existing system architecture based on hot anode gas recirculation, steam reforming and a modular interface between the gas processing unit and the stack module has been expanded with functionalities like a heat recovery for hot water production, an exhaust gas condensate recovery unit, and power electronics for grid feed-in. Besides that, an optimized integration of the BoP components such as the hot anode gas recirculation blower, development of periphery components for stand-alone applications, activities towards design to manufacture as well as load following operation capabilities and long term operational durability are in the center of development activities. This work gives an insight into the development achievements that are the next step towards industrialized SOFC CHP systems as well as operational data for full- and part load operating points, as well as transient- and load following operation.

Introduction

The SOFC5-60 project aims towards the development of a 5 kW_{el} SOFC CHP (Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Combined Heat and Power) system for residential and non-residential applications such as hotels, small industries and multi-family homes (see Figure 1). The project is funded in Germany (Projekträger Jülich, PNr.: 03ET6120A) and Austria (FFG, PNr.: 864851) and consists of following consortium; AVL List, BIOS Bioenergiesysteme, MIBA HTC, Forschung Burgenland (Austrian partners), Viessmann/Hexis, Fraunhofer IKTS and AVL Schrick (German partners). The project lasts from 04/2017 to 03/2021. The product targets at an electrical efficiency of 60 %. Furthermore, the heat recovery development aims at an overall plant efficiency of 95% (related to the NCV of natural gas input into the SOFC) by using the recovered heat from the exhaust gas of the SOFC for domestic hot water supply of the customers (e.g. apartment buildings, hotels). Within the SOFC5-60 project an electrical efficiency of 55 % is targeted since not all components can be customized as required to meet the product requirements (e.g.: power electronics). However, the resulting system design will be the basis for an industrialization.

Figure 1: Target applications of SOFC CHP system

Further targets of the SOFC5-60 project and the related product can be seen in Table 1. The system operates on natural gas or bio methane and was designed with respect to low system CAPEX (Capital Expenditure <2000 EUR/kW_{el} based on high volumes), high lifetimes (80.000 h) and a wide power modulation range including load following capability to achieve a high number of full load hours over the year (>6000 h). The results of a previous functional demonstration platform formed the basis for further fundamental development and customization addressing the final power range and product requirements.

Table 1: System targets

QUANTITATIVE TARGETS AND RESULTS		TARGETS Product	TARGETS SOFC5-60
Rated electrical power (BoL, AC, net)	[kW]	5	5
Electrical efficiency (BoL, AC, net, LHV)	[%]	60	55
Total efficiency (LHV)	[%]	95 ¹⁾	90 ¹⁾
Stack module lifetime	[h]	80,000	30,000 ²⁾
System lifetime	[y]	20	5 ³⁾
Demonstrated system lifetime	[h]	20,000	5,000
Power modulation	[%]	<50 %, t.b.d.	<50 %
CAPEX @ 1000 units/year	[EUR/kW]	<2000	prognosis
Emission limit (CO/NO _x /SO _x)	[mg/kWh]	50/30/5	50/30/5
Noise emission (sound power level)	[dB(A)]	50	to be investigated
¹⁾ Based on 35 °C exhaust gas temperature			
²⁾ Will be extrapolated from 5000 h test			
³⁾ Lifetime of BoP components will be extrapolated from durability testing			

Eventually, the system will be integrated in an office building at Forschung Burgenland and thus validated under real life environment conditions to achieve a field-test-ready system at the end of the project for a subsequently planned field test programme.

1. Scientific Approach

First, building load profiles were analysed in order to determine the appropriate target for power output (5 kW_{AC,net}) and system efficiency (55/90 %). Based on the system requirements and the CFY stack technology of IKTS a new SOFC system architecture in terms of the flow sheet design and the packaging was developed by AVL. The main features are (i) the integration of a customized stack module for the desired power output, (ii) an off-the shelf power electronics for DC/DC and DC/AC conversion, (iii) the mechanical and thermal integration of an improved hot anode gas blower for anode gas recirculation, (iv) the integration of highly efficient heat recovery unit for hot water production, (v) an exhaust gas blower for underpressure operation, (vi) a desulfurization unit for natural gas and (vii) a condensate cleaning unit for condensing water recycle. The main focus of the development is on the one hand the optimization of the electrical efficiency as well as the definition of manufacturing and certification requirements for the product development stage. Furthermore, a detailed lifetime analysis has been carried out in order to size the stack module in terms of the number of stacks to meet 30,000 h of stack lifetime. Eventually, the control system including control and operating procedures for a fully automated operation are developed by AVL.

2. Simulations, Experiments and Design

Building load profiles (Forschung Burgenland)

Load profile analysis is a decisive procedure for designing CHP-systems. Particularly the time-resolved electrical and thermal energy demand information are mandatory for determining the required range of capacity and heat to power ratio. The computation of representative load profiles for multifamily houses based on standardized consumptions or limited datasets can lead to a peak overestimation and statistically irrelevant outcomes. Stochastic models, which considers the occupancy pattern, different technical appliances,

seasonal effects, household categories etc., can overcome these drawbacks and can provide beneficial information about the energy demand on a sub-hourly time scale. Hence, for the requirement definitions of the SOFC-system individualized, stochastic load profiles were generated with the simulation tool synPRO ([1], [2]). The investigations were carried out for different residential buildings (2 single-family houses, 22 multi-family houses and 12 semi-detached houses) and year of construction (between 2002 and 2017).

The waste heat utilization for domestic hot water (DHW) production facilitate an efficient year-round operation and the exploitation of the high exhaust temperature level of the SOFC-system. Therefore, the DHW application is the most promising integration scenario for residential buildings. For such application the ideal heat to power ratio can be identified based on the analysis of the generated electrical and DHW load profiles. In order to get a more efficient CHP system solution, normally a buffer tank will be used to avoid peak loads and to decouple the electrical and hot water demand. For this reason the heat to power ratio distribution were computed based on daily-averaged values. The left diagram in Figure 2 represents a typical frequency distribution of the required heat to power ratios for one year. Accordingly, it can be expected that the most frequently heat to power ratio is near 0.6, which fit well the addressed product and project targets (cf. Table 1).

Figure 2: Left: Frequency distribution of the required heat to power ratio for CHP-system
Right: Electrical load duration curve for one of the investigated residential building

In addition to the required heat to power ratios the load duration curves for the residential buildings were analyzed based on a time interval of 15 min. The right line plot in Figure 2 represents a typical load duration curve for a multi-family house with 9 apartments. The curve illustrates the required electrical capacity range of the SOFC-system. If a non-feed-in operation is aspired and the modulation range capture 2.5 to 5.0 kW_{el} the SOFC-system can cover 40% of the annual electrical energy demand. If the modulation range will be increased from 1.0 to 5.0 kW_{el} the cover ratio grows up to about 86%.

Process simulation of the SOFC CHP system (AVL)

A detailed 0/1D process simulation in matlab/Simulink was carried out to define the process conditions and component requirements. Different system architectures considering two different recirculation concepts (blower vs. ejector based), stack module size, component efficiencies and achievable lifetimes were investigated. Furthermore, full load, part load, beginning and end of life operating points were considered. The end of life criteria was defined to be 4 kW_{AC,net} at constant current operation. The process is based on natural gas steam reforming. Figure 3 shows the Sankey diagram of the efficiency and power flow for the 100 % beginning of life (BoL) operating point. A DC gross efficiency of

63 % at 310 mA/cm² and 830 °C based on a global stack module ASR of 0.493 Ohm*cm² is achieved. Considering the power consumption of the blowers and other periphery components as well as the power conversion a AC net efficiency of 55 % is calculated. The heat in the exhaust gas is recovered down to 30.3 °C to make use of the condensing heat and thus achieve an overall efficiency of 90 %.

Figure 3: Sankey diagram of the efficiency and power flow

Further operating points at part load, heat-up and end of life were simulated as required for the following component developments.

Ejector development (AVL)

As an alternative to the hot anode gas recirculation blower an ejector based recirculation was considered in the beginning of the project. The ejector would be operated by an increased primary natural gas inlet pressure of >2 barg in order to achieve an anode gas recirculation ratio of 70 %. The ejector must overcome the pressure drop between the outlet and the secondary inlet. This pressure drop is mainly created by the reformer, the anode gas heat exchanger and the anode side of the stack module and amounts to 20 – 30 mbar. The relatively high pressure drop requires a well designed ejector geometry in order to reduce pressure losses between the primary inlet and the diffuser to a minimum. Only then a high efficiency of the ejector can be achieved. The ejector was simulated in AVL FIRE (CFD software tool) at various operating conditions in terms of primary pressure, temperature at primary and secondary inlet and gas compositions.

Figure 4: CFD simulation of ejector for anode gas recirculation

Figure 5 shows the comparison of the electric blower power needed for 70 % recirculation ratio at a pressure drop of 15 mbar between ejector outlet and ejector secondary inlet. The aim was to investigate which of the options leads to a lower electrical power consumption. Assuming a blower efficiency of 10 % for the hot anode gas recirculation blower ($t_{in}=648$ °C, $m=1.119$ g/s) and 20 – 30 % for a natural gas blower ($t_{in}=20$ °C, $m=0.172$ g/s) the

ejector would require a primary inlet pressures below 1.6 – 1.9 barg in order to be more efficient. Since CFD simulation has shown that a significantly higher pressure would be needed at the ejector inlet to reach the same recirculation ratio it was decided that the anode gas recirculation blower solution will be more efficient.

Figure 5: Comparison of blower power for ejector and hot anode gas recirculation blower

Hot anode gas recirculation blower development (AVL Schrick)

The development targets for the blower were and requirements of the SOFC5-60 blower have been:

- Recirculate temperatures up to 600°C
- >10% efficiency (electric-to-flow dynamic)
- Pressure ratio of 1,04 @ a recirculation mass flow of 2,1 g/s
- Liquid-cooling of e-motor stator
- Main accessibility from back-side due to installation requirements into the SOFC-system

While Figure 6 (left) shows the Mk1-design in a cross-section the prototype is displayed in Figure 6 (right).

Figure 6: Blower Design Mk1 (left) and prototype (right)

As it can be seen in the cross-section the blower design utilizes an oil-based full-floating bearing concept. Main driver for choice of this bearing concept is the thermal management of the blower system as the maximum capable temperature of the e-motors permanent-magnets is far below the 600°C of the anode gas which is surrounding the compressor

wheel in a one-shaft design directly connected – and therefore conducting – to the rotor magnets. So, the lubrication mass flow of the compressor-side bearing sleeve is significantly contributing to shaft-cooling and therefore thermal protection of rotor magnets. Cooling of the e-motor stator – which is capable for maximum 120°C – is realized with an active coolant circuit which is integrated into the thermal circuit of the overall SOFC-system and therefore contributes to the hot water provision of the entire system.

Within initial testing of Mk. 1 of hot anode recirculation blower general functionality could be proven but it has been figured out that efficiency targets could not be reached. To improve the situation different optimization measures have been investigated and finally converted to a Mk. 2 design.

In Figure 7 a comparison of Mk. 1 and Mk. 2 design is shown.

Figure 7: Comparison Mk1 and Mk2

The upgrades contain the following single measures:

- Reduction of active length of electric motor → load-point shift towards lower power consumption
- Re-work of bearing gap layout → feasible due to shortened rotor and therefore more robust rotordynamic behaviour
- Reduction of bearing diameters from 7mm to 6mm → reduction of frictional losses

Prototypes of Mk. 2 design are currently within assembly process and will afterwards prove the effectiveness of the taken measures to improve the efficiency of the hot anode recirculation blower.

Heat recovery development (BIOS)

In order to identify the suitable size of the heat consumers, typical electricity and heat demand profiles of residential buildings with 9 to 40 dwellings and 20 to 80 inhabitants have been selected for TRNSYS simulations. To reach highest annual full load operation hours and highest electricity generation, the simulations revealed, that the control strategy needs to be adapted to the consumer structure and that a heat controlled instead of an electricity controlled operation is more meaningful for residential clients. A 5 kW_{el} SOFC system is suitable for an apartment building with about 25-30 inhabitants. By the provision of domestic hot water, a heat controlled operation at high load during the whole year can be achieved. In addition, the option of domestic hot water production bears the advantage that the heat exchanger can operate in condensing mode because the return water temperature from the buffer storage tank typically amounts to only 20-25 °C and thus a high heat recovery potential of sensible and latent heat is given.

For the screening of suitable condensing heat exchangers (HX) 10 manufacturers of various HX types were asked whether their product portfolio contains heat exchangers

suitable for the given boundary conditions and the requested requirements such as reasonable pressure drop, low temperature difference and acceptable size.

At the end of the screening process two types, a plate HX and a radial HX remained and were further evaluated by means of CFD simulations. As one result of this work, the temperature distributions for the radial and the plate HX are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Iso surfaces of the exhaust gas temperature [°C] in a vertical axis cut through the radial HX (left) and a vertical axis cut and a first pass gas section cut through the plate HX (centre and right)

The temperature difference between exhaust gas outlet and water return is much smaller for the plate HX (<5°C) than for the radial HX (17°C), which leads to a considerably higher efficiency of the plate HX. In combination with the other advantages (more compact design, flexibility, price) this type of heat exchanger has been selected and subsequently has been further optimised by CFD simulations for the specific application in the SOFC system.

Subsequently the condensing HX has been built and tested. The performance evaluation was done at a specially designed heat exchanger test rig under representative operation conditions. The results show that the expected target design values regarding temperature difference between gas outlet and water return (4°C) and HX efficiency (79%; = thermal output/thermal input x 100) at a water return temperature of 30°C could be kept. According to TRNSYS simulations over a whole year, the HX efficiency will increase to 85%, considering a typical average domestic water return temperature of 24°C. This high efficiency of the HX results in an overall annual utilisation rate of the SOFC system of close to 95% (meeting the target design value).

The condenser has now been implemented in the overall SOFC testing unit and will be evaluated regarding its performance under real system conditions in steady state as well as in transient operation as a next step.

Stack module development (IKTS)

The development includes efforts on interconnect, cell and stack level to decrease degradation and increase power density of the stacks as well as on process design,

mechanical and electrical balance of plant component development and system packaging. The main interest of the IKTS MK35x stack development is reducing costs by new method of interconnect manufacturing and improving long term stability by new protection layer. A more stable electrode with less reforming capability will be developed and validated. For validation of components for stacks a standard procedure were specified based on performance map, 3000 h long term operation and start stop cycling tests. The quality of measurements were improved and tests were focused on the uncertainty of measurement to separate measurement or infrastructure errors from real degradation [3]. Under consideration of these impacts it is possible to use acceleration parameters for tests to shorten the validation period and estimate durability for 30,000 h or more.

Stacks will be combined to a stack module to reach the estimated power output based on existing know how with the focus on a design which is easy to scale up.

Experiments with new stack components for MK35x and reference tests for durability were conducted on the actual MK352 design, the new design Mk353 and were flanked with sample tests. Based on the performance map of a 10 cell MK352 stack with defined gases from simulation, 200 layers were an optimal size for the stack module of the system to get an power output of 5.7 kW_{el} at 100 % BoL. Furthermore, the number of cells were chosen with respect to the lifetime target.

For reasons of mechanical compression, easier assembly and tightness a “one tower assembly” were chosen. CFD-simulation have shown that an external gas manifold parallel to the internal stack manifold is necessary to reach an adequate uniformity. With the separate manifolding of two packages of 100 cells (see Figure 9) the maximum fuel utilization of the 200 cell configuration is only 2 % higher than the average.

Figure 9: Sliced CAD model of the stack module showing each 100 cell towers

Two separate stack modules were successfully assembled and tested with power output BoL 100 %, 5.74 kW_{el} and BoL 50 % 2.7 kW_{el} at IKTS. Both modules have comparable quality of power output with a difference of only 51 W (1 %) contributed to an optimized thermal insulation of one of the two stack modules. The variation of fuel utilization η_{FU} = 60-85% at the 100% operation point (BoL) with 39.4 A shows a minor dependency on the electrical power output from 5.9 to 5.6 kW_{el}.

The median ASR of the stacks were calculated with 0.50-0.58 Ohm*cm² and therefore is a little bit higher than estimated at the simulation.

Figure 10: Left: Power output of stack module @100% BoL, 39.4 A, reformat gas and different η_{FU} , Right: Heat-up of stack module from room temperature to 100 % BoL

The startup procedure (see Figure 10 right) was adjusted to proceed as fast as possible from room temperature into operation based on system conditions. After 7,5 hours a stable operation point at 100% BoL was reached. The operating strategy was developed with regard to system operation focusing on the minimum stack temperature at which current drawing can be started. The transition from a heat-up through heated cathode gas to a thermally self-sustaining power generation and thus stack internal heat production was optimized in order to accelerate the heat-up time until full load. The performance characteristics of the stack at lower temperatures also define the dynamics of the system operation in low part load as well as for a re-start from hot stand-by conditions.

System design (AVL)

Based on the results of the process simulation and the individual component developments a completely new design for the 5 kW SOFC system was developed (see Figure 11). The design aims at a highly integrated packaging with at the same time good accessibility for service and maintenance.

Figure 11: 5 kW SOFC CHP system

System commissioning (AVL)

The Gen.1 system including all new features focusing on the stack module, hot anode gas recirculation blower, heat recovery and the power conversion was commissioned. Various operating functions such as the heat-up, the anode gas blower operation in underpressure conditions, the reforming, the condensate removal and recycle path from the heat recovery, the power conversion path from stack module DC output to grid AC input as well as different operating points up to 50 % part load were tested. The results are the basis for the design of the planned Gen.2 within the project.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

The electricity and heat demand profile of building consumers were investigated in detail in order to define the system requirements in terms of power output, power modulation and the optimal split between electricity and heat production. Further, product and system requirements were defined as basis for the system development. A new process design, component development as well as the system design and build-up for the Gen.1 5 kW SOFC CHP system was completed and commissioned. An anode gas blower based recirculation concept was chosen over an ejector based solution due to the higher efficiency potential based on the specific boundary conditions for the application. A highly efficient heat recovery was successfully simulated and tested. An off-the shelf power conversion system was integrated and operated in grid feed-in operation mode. The MK35x stacks and the assembled stack modules are a robust component for the CHP system and fulfil the requirements of operation from Gen.1. The target power output of the stack module of 5740 W_{el} at the conditions for the 100 % BoL was successfully reached. Optimization of air supply and isolation will lead to homogeneous temperature distribution inside the stack module and an increased operation window. Improved stack components with lower ASR and degradation rates as well as better connection between the stacks by an optimized electric- and gas interface will be the focus of Gen.2. The one tower stack module design opens an easy adaption of power output by variation of cells in one tower and in mirroring to two or four tower configuration. The findings are currently implemented in the design of the Gen.2. build-up and full validation is planned to be started later this year.

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